

Institute of Pedagogy of NAES of Ukraine

Department of monitoring and evaluation of the quality
of general secondary education

Antonina Hryvko, Svitlana Naumenko

THE USE OF EDUCATIONAL MONITORING RESULTS IN TEACHING PRACTICE IN UKRAINIAN SCHOOLS

Study Description

2026

Authors: Antonina Hryvko, PhD in Pedagogical Sciences, Senior Researcher, Senior Research Fellow at the Department of monitoring and evaluation of the quality of general secondary education, Institute of Pedagogy of NAES of Ukraine.

Svitlana Naumenko, PhD in Pedagogical Sciences, Senior Researcher, Leading Research Fellow at the Department of monitoring and evaluation of the quality of general secondary education, Institute of Pedagogy of NAES of Ukraine.

The description of the study outlines the aim and relevance of the research “The use of educational monitoring results in teaching practice in Ukrainian schools”, conducted in 2025–2026 by researchers of the Department of monitoring and evaluation of the quality of general secondary education at the Institute of pedagogy of National academy of educational studies of Ukraine. It provides information on the research instruments, sampling procedures, and the recruitment of survey participants.

The document is intended for researchers examining teaching practice in general secondary education, specialists in teacher professional education, educational analysts, experts in education quality management, and policymakers.

Citation: Hryvko, A., & Naumenko, S. (2026). The use of educational monitoring results in teaching practice in Ukrainian schools: Study Description.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20085868>

Funding: The study was carried out within the framework of the research project “Methodology for assessing the impact of the results of international and national monitoring studies of education quality on the development of general secondary education in Ukraine”, implemented by the Department of monitoring and evaluation of the quality of general secondary education at the Institute of pedagogy of NAES of Ukraine. State registration number of the research project: 0126U000643.

Organization: Institute of Pedagogy of NAES of Ukraine
52-D Sichovykh Striltsiv Street
Kyiv, 04053
Ukraine

Copyright: Creative Commons: Attribution CC BY 4.0. Materials distributed under the Creative Commons license may be used by third parties under the conditions defined by the authors. These materials may be shared, copied, freely used, and distributed in any form, provided that appropriate authorship attribution is given.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY	4
2. DATA COLLECTION	7
2.1. TARGET GROUP OF SURVEY PARTICIPANTS AND SAMPLE FORMATION	7
2.2. PROCEDURE FOR RECRUITING SURVEY PARTICIPANTS	9
3. RESEARCH DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENTS AND DATA ORGANISATION	10
3.1. QUESTIONNAIRE	10
3.2. DATA STRUCTURE AND AVAILABILITY	12
4. STRUCTURE AND NAMING OF OPEN-ACCESS FILES	14
5. APPENDICES	15
APPENDIX A.....	15
APPENDIX B.....	17
REFERENCES	18

1. GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY

Over the past two decades, in most OECD countries, the use of educational monitoring results in teaching practice has become a policy imperative¹. International organizations, national governments, and professional communities have increasingly articulated the expectation that teachers should rely on educational monitoring data to improve the quality of teaching and learning, make pedagogical decisions, and support their own professional development². The Law of Ukraine *On Education*³ defines education quality monitoring as a system of “successive and systematic measures ... aimed at identifying and tracking trends in the development of education quality”, while contemporary education policy increasingly positions it not merely as a procedure for recording learning outcomes, but as a tool for quality management, reform evaluation, and support for pedagogical development⁴. In this context, decision-making based on educational monitoring data emerges as a key competence of the contemporary teacher and, at the same time, as a systemic requirement for schools.

However, there remains a substantial gap between the declared importance of educational monitoring studies and the actual use of their results in the classroom, a gap that remains insufficiently explored both theoretically and empirically. In Ukrainian academic discourse, issues related to education quality monitoring have been addressed primarily at the level of theoretical and methodological foundations, organizational and managerial mechanisms, and regulatory frameworks. A separate body of academic and official materials has also been devoted to the results of specific monitoring cycles. Notably, reports based on the results of monitoring studies of primary education quality (Ukrainian Center for

¹ Schlicht-Schmälzle, R. et al. (2024). Bridging the research-practice gap in education. *OECD Education Working Papers*, No. 319. <https://doi.org/10.1787/c0d3f781-en>

² Bauer, J., & Kollar, I. (2023). (Wie) kann die Nutzung bildungswissenschaftlicher Evidenz Lehren und Lernen verbessern? Thesen und Fragen zur Diskussion um evidenzorientiertes Denken und Handeln von Lehrkräften. *Unterrichtswissenschaft*, 51, 123–147. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42010-023-00166-1>

Nelson, J., & Campbell, C. (2017). Evidence-informed practice in education: Meanings and applications. *Educational Research*, 59(2), 127–135. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2017.1314115>

³ ВРУ (2017). Закон України про освіту. *Відомості Верховної Ради*, № 38-39, ст.380

⁴ Schildkamp, K. (2019). Data-based decision-making for school improvement: Research insights and gaps. *Educational Research*, 61(3), 257–273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2019.1625716>

Schildkamp, K., Karbautzki, L., & Vanhoof, J. (2014). Exploring data use practices around Europe: Identifying enablers and barriers. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 42, 15–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2013.10.007>

Schildkamp, K., Poortman, C. L., Luyten, H., & Ebbeler, J. (2017). Factors promoting and hindering data-based decision making in schools. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 28(2), 242–258. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2016.1256901>

Educational Quality Assessment, 2021; 2024) contain practical recommendations for teachers. However, the question of what happens to monitoring results after their publication, whether they reach teachers, how they are interpreted, and in which practices they are implemented, has not yet become the subject of systematic empirical analysis.

It is precisely this relationship between the production of data and their pedagogical reception that constitutes the central object of the proposed study, “The Use of Educational Monitoring Results in Teaching Practice in Ukrainian Schools” (hereinafter referred to as the *study*).

Aim and Research Questions

The aim of the study is to examine the specific features of using educational monitoring results in the professional activity of teachers in Ukrainian general secondary education institutions.

The study addresses the following questions:

1. What experience do teachers and general secondary education institutions have in participating in international, national, and regional monitoring studies?
2. To what extent do teachers assess their own awareness of educational monitoring results?
3. At what levels, how often, and for what purposes are these results used in teaching practice?
4. What factors prevent teachers from using educational research results?
5. How do teachers assess the reliability and realism of monitoring results?
6. How effective are educational monitoring studies according to teachers themselves?
7. What, in teachers’ opinion, could enhance the practical relevance of monitoring studies for school practice?

Scientific Significance and Practical Value of the Study

The scientific novelty of this study lies in shifting the analytical focus from the macro level of education policy and the organization of monitoring studies to the micro level of everyday teaching practice. This shift in perspective makes it

possible to examine what usually remains beyond the scope of systematic analysis, namely the mechanisms of teachers' reception of data, the conditions under which such data are transformed into practical decisions, and the factors that hinder or facilitate the use of educational research data.

The theoretical significance of the study lies in clarifying the relationship between external assessment systems and the actual mechanisms of decision-making at the teacher level. In international academic literature, this relationship is the subject of active debate, while in the context of post-Soviet education systems it remains insufficiently studied.

The practical value of the study lies in developing evidence-based grounds for improving the formats in which monitoring results are presented, designing professional development programs aimed at strengthening teachers' competences related to the use of educational research data, and shaping school policies that support teachers' work with educational research data.

The study results are expected to be of interest to education authorities, researchers in the fields of educational measurement and educational management, developers of monitoring instruments, and teaching staffs, both in Ukraine and in a comparative international context.

The study is part of the research project of the Department of monitoring and evaluation of the quality of general secondary education at the Institute of pedagogy of the National academy of educational sciences of Ukraine (hereinafter – NAES) entitled “Methodology for assessing the impact of the results of international and national monitoring studies of education quality on the development of general secondary education in Ukraine”. The state registration number of the research project is 0126U000643. The implementation period is 1 January 2026 to 31 December 2027. An information note about the study and its research team is provided in Appendix A.

2. DATA COLLECTION

For the purposes of the survey, an original questionnaire for teachers was developed by L. Vashchenko, A. Hryvko, and Yu. Zhuk. The questionnaire underwent expert validation to ensure the quality of its content and structure. The review process involved researchers from the Department of monitoring and evaluation of the quality of general secondary education at the Institute of pedagogy of NAES of Ukraine. The content of the questionnaire is described in Section 3.1 of this document.

The developed questionnaire was placed on the online platform Qualtrics XM. Data collection was conducted during November and December 2025.

2.1. Target group of survey participants and sample formation

The target group of survey participants consisted of teachers working at all three levels of general secondary education in Ukraine: primary education, covering Grades 1–4 (ISCED 1 level); basic secondary education, covering Grades 5–9 (ISCED 2 level); and upper secondary education, covering Grades 10–11 (ISCED 3 level)⁵.

The study sample was formed using a non-probability sampling approach. The resulting sample may be characterized as non-random, combining elements of respondent self-selection.

All participants were fully informed about the study, including its aim, structure, data collection, data processing, and data protection procedures, and provided informed consent to participate in digital form, as presented in Appendix B.

As a result of the survey, 18,581 completed questionnaires were collected. Information on the study data collection is summarized in Table 1.

⁵ISCED = International Standard Classification of Education

UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (2012). *International Standard Classification of Education: ISCED 2011*.

UNESCO. <https://uis.unesco.org/sites/default/files/documents/international-standard-classification-of-education-isced-2011-en.pdf>

Table 1:
Information on the specific features of data collection within the study “The use of educational monitoring results in teaching practice in Ukrainian schools”

Data collection parameter	Description
Duration of data collection	November–December 2025
Geographical coverage	Vinnitsia, Volyn, Dnipropetrovsk, Donetsk, Zhytomyr, Zakarpattia, Zaporizhzhia, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Kirovohrad, Lviv, Mykolaiv, Odesa, Poltava, Rivne, Sumy, Ternopil, Kharkiv, Kherson, Khmelnytskyi, Cherkasy, Chernivtsi, Chernihiv regions, and the city of Kyiv
Study population	Teachers of secondary schools
Unit of analysis	Individuals, namely teachers
Approach to participant selection or sample formation	Non-random sample: convenience sample with elements of self-selection
Participant selection procedure	Invitations to participate distributed through secondary schools
Target sample size (N)	Not applicable
Actual sample size (n)	18,581 respondents
Data collection method	Self-administered online questionnaire, standardized computer-based survey
Type of data	Numerical and verbal data
Topics	Socio-demographic data and teacher characteristics; characteristics of the schools; experience of participation in monitoring studies of education quality; awareness of monitoring study results; level, frequency, and purposes of using monitoring results in teaching practice; barriers to the use of monitoring results; teachers’ attitudes towards monitoring studies; needs concerning the formats for presenting monitoring results
Ethical principles	Voluntary participation; anonymity; no personal data were collected

2.2. Procedure for recruiting survey participants

Teachers were recruited for the survey through three main channels. First, recruitment was conducted through the departments or offices of education and science of regional and Kyiv city state administrations, which disseminated information about the survey among general secondary schools. Second, recruitment was carried out through regional institutions of postgraduate teacher education, which received a request to share information about the survey with teachers participating in professional development courses during the survey period. Third, information about the survey could be communicated directly to teaching staff by the administrations of secondary schools.

The invitation letter to participate in the survey, which contained a link to the online questionnaire, was distributed by the Institute of Pedagogy of NAES of Ukraine on 18 November 2025. The letter explained the aim of the survey and provided information on the specific conditions of teachers' participation, including anonymity and voluntariness. It also described the further use of the research data exclusively for educational and scientific purposes and outlined the procedure for publishing the results.

3. RESEARCH DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENTS AND DATA ORGANISATION

3.1. Questionnaire

The original questionnaire for school teachers, hereinafter referred to as the Questionnaire, covered seven thematic blocks, as shown in Table 2. It is a combined instrument rather than a homogeneous psychometric scale. The Questionnaire includes nominal single-choice and multiple-choice questions, ordinal five-point scales, and open-ended text questions that perform different functions, ranging from describing respondents' characteristics to measuring the intensity or frequency of the phenomena under study. Detailed information on the variables and their statistical characteristics is provided in the codebook.

Table 2:
Questionnaire content and question format

Thematic blocks of the survey	Question content	Question format
Personal information, teacher characteristics	Age	Short open-ended response, numerical
	Gender	Single choice
	Level of education	Single choice
	Teaching experience	Single choice, ranges
	Subject or subjects taught	Multiple choice with an open-ended option
Characteristics of the education institution	Type of settlement	Single choice
	Level of general secondary education provided by the institution: primary, basic, or upper secondary school	Multiple choice
	Location of the education institution, region	Single choice
Experience of participation in educational monitoring studies	Teachers' participation in monitoring studies	Single choice, yes or no
	Students' participation in monitoring studies	Single choice, yes or no
	Titles of monitoring studies	Multiple choice with an open-ended text response option
Awareness of educational monitoring results	Level of awareness of monitoring results	Likert scale
	Sources of information about monitoring results	Multiple choice

Thematic blocks of the survey	Question content	Question format
	Forms in which information about monitoring results is received	Multiple choice with an open-ended short text response option
	Availability of practice-oriented conclusions or recommendations based on monitoring results	Single choice, yes or no
Use of educational monitoring results	Level and frequency of using monitoring results in school practice	Matrix with single choice
	Purposes of using monitoring results	Multiple choice
Barriers to the use of educational monitoring results	Barriers to using monitoring results	Multiple choice with an open-ended short text response option
Teachers' attitudes towards educational monitoring studies	Extent to which monitoring results reflect students' actual achievements	Likert scale
	Level of effectiveness of monitoring studies in improving education quality	Likert scale
Enhancing the practical relevance of monitoring studies for teachers	Teachers' views on possibilities for increasing the practical relevance of monitoring studies	Open-ended text response

3.2. Data structure and availability

The data obtained within this study have been published as a Scientific Use File (SUF). Prior to publication, the dataset underwent thorough cleaning and formal checks for consistency and plausibility. The survey data were anonymous from the outset of data collection. No personal data of participants, including names, surnames, email addresses, or IP addresses, were collected or stored. This makes it impossible to identify respondents or establish their affiliation with a specific education institution.

The SUF of the survey dataset contains one row, or observation, for each

teacher who provided an answer to at least one question from the block of core questions. Detailed information on the structure of the dataset, the variables, and their statistical characteristics is provided in the codebook.

The research data have been deposited in Zenodo as open access (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20083232](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20083232)). Proper citation of the study is a mandatory condition for using the data in any publications prepared on the basis of the SUF.

4. STRUCTURE AND NAMING OF OPEN-ACCESS FILES

The research data publication is accompanied by documentation comprising the study description, the questionnaire, and the codebook.

The titles and content of the documents are presented in Table 3.

Table 3:
Data and supporting documents of the study “The use of educational monitoring results in teaching practice in Ukrainian schools”

Document	File name
Teacher survey data	mondata-ped-use_2026_teas_suf_v1-0.csv
Study description	mondata-ped-use_2026_sd_ENG_v1-0.pdf
Questionnaire	mondata-ped-use_2026_quest_ENG_v1-0.pdf
Codebook	mondata-ped-use_2026_cb_ENG_v1-0.pdf

5. APPENDICES

Appendix A

Table A1:
Information note on the study

Information about the study	Details
Institution where the study was conducted	Institute of Pedagogy of National academy of educational studies of Ukraine
State registration number of the research project	0126U000643
Topic of the research project	Methodology for Assessing the Impact of the Results of International and National Monitoring Studies of Education Quality on the Development of General Secondary Education in Ukraine
Duration of the research project	1 January 2026 – 31 December 2027
Title of the study	The use of educational monitoring results in teaching practice in Ukrainian schools
Classification of the study subject	External assessment of education quality; teachers' professional activity
Main field of research	Educational sociology; educational research
Keywords	Teacher survey; general secondary education institutions; educational monitoring studies; educational research results; educational data; teaching practice; teaching experience; teachers' perceptions.

Table A2:
Research Team

Name and position of the researcher in the department*	Researcher digital identifier, ORCID	Role in the study
Svitlana Alekseeva, Head of Department	0000-0002-8132-0465	Scientific supervisor of the department's research project
Antonina Hryvko, Senior Research Fellow	0000-0001-9460-4777	Study coordinator; work package leader; researcher
Yurii Zhuk, Chief Research Fellow of the Department	0000-0002-6932-2484	Researcher
Lidiia Vashchenko, Senior Research Fellow of the Department	0000-0002-0637-2142	Researcher
Svitlana Naumenko, Leading Research Fellow of the Department	0000-0002-8279-4427	Researcher

* Department of monitoring and evaluation of the quality of general secondary education, Institute of pedagogy of NAES of Ukraine.

Appendix B

Digital Informed Consent Form for Participation in the Study

Dear colleagues,

We invite you to participate in a survey aimed at examining the specific features of using the results of external monitoring studies, both national and international, designed to assess the quality of education in the pedagogical practice of general secondary education institutions.

The responses received will be used in aggregated form for research and analytical purposes. Participation in the survey is voluntary, and responses are anonymous.

Thank you for your time!

By continuing to complete the questionnaire, you confirm that you have read the information provided, understand the conditions of participation, and give your informed consent to participate in the survey and to the use of your responses in aggregated form:

I agree that my responses to the questionnaire will be used for the stated research purposes, provided that they do not contain information that could personally identify me, in accordance with the Law of Ukraine “On Personal Data Protection” No. 2297-VI, 2010, as amended in 2024.

REFERENCES

- Bauer, J., & Kollar, I. (2023). (Wie) kann die Nutzung bildungswissenschaftlicher Evidenz Lehren und Lernen verbessern? Thesen und Fragen zur Diskussion um evidenzorientiertes Denken und Handeln von Lehrkräften. *Unterrichtswissenschaft*, *51*, 123–147. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42010-023-00166-1>
- Nelson, J., & Campbell, C. (2017). Evidence-informed practice in education: Meanings and applications. *Educational Research*, *59*(2), 127–135. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2017.1314115>
- Schildkamp, K. (2019). Data-based decision-making for school improvement: Research insights and gaps. *Educational Research*, *61*(3), 257–273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2019.1625716>
- Schildkamp, K., Karbautzki, L., & Vanhoof, J. (2014). Exploring data use practices around Europe: Identifying enablers and barriers. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, *42*, 15–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2013.10.007>
- Schildkamp, K., Poortman, C. L., Luyten, H., & Ebbeler, J. (2017). Factors promoting and hindering data-based decision making in schools. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, *28*(2), 242–258. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2016.1256901>
- Schlicht-Schmälzle, R. et al. (2024). Bridging the research-practice gap in education. *OECD Education Working Papers*, No. 319. <https://doi.org/10.1787/c0d3f781-en>
- Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine (2017). Law of Ukraine on Education. Bulletin of the Verkhovna Rada, No. 38–39, p. 380